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Improve Listening Comprehension In English

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Abstract

This research aims to find out how to improve listening comprehension in English in Uinsu students of the 2nd semester education management study program to improve listening comprehension in English. This research explores the extent to which students improve listening comprehension through films with and without subtitles, music, radio, and heard podcasts in English and what was their attitude towards this teaching tool. In order to be able to hear well, understand the meaning of each word, sentence, when talking to the other person in English. This research used qualitative methods, namely interviews and observations carried out directly in the MPI 2 class, interviews with several students and forming study groups to carry out teaching in improving listening comprehension in English, and taking several documentation as evidence that the research had been carried out. The results of this research are that MP2 class students' listening comprehension in English has increased after learning in study groups. Ways to improve students' listening comprehension in English are by watching films, listening to the radio, listening to music, and listening to podcasts in English. In this way students are able to improve their listening comprehension in English

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INTRODUCTION

English is an international language and a means of communication throughout the world. English language proficiency is the skill of understanding spoken and written language and is expressed in four categories: listening, speaking, reading, and writing (Dalimunthe & Ihsan, 2021). Learning English does not only involve planning, implementation and evaluation, but also the supporting capacity of professional staff and infrastructure (Sya & Helmanto, 2020). Foreign language teaching has developed in Indonesia in line with society's need for the importance of language skills in the era of globalization (Adnyana, 2022). A number of studies have proven that listening comprehension can be improved by the addition of pictures (Bowen, 1982; Guichon & McLornan, 2008; Hanley, Herron & Cole, 1995; Lonergan, 1984; Markham, Peter & McCarthy, 2001; Stempleski, 2003; Tomalin, 1986) . So, apart from the fact that films are a motivating medium because they cover a variety of topics and are presented with audio and visual stimuli (Lonergan, 1984; Stempleski, 2003), the benefit of using them in language learning is that the images and sounds help to organize. it1. The introduction of event scenes and additional information, such as paralinguistic features, is provided as support for listening comprehension (Guichon & McLornan, 2008; Katchen, 1996a). With advances in technology, the choices of how to watch films have become many. Apart from that, films can also fill the cultural gap that is sometimes a prerequisite for learning vocabulary, namely a combination of novels in English that specifically focus on interpreting the meaning. Sila? . or mistranslated.(p.102).

The use of films appears to remain limited or underutilized because much research has focused on exploring whether the use of L1 or L2 subtitles helps learners' general auditory comprehension (Baltova, 1999; Guichon & McLornan, 2008; Markham et al., 2001) rather than their actual language acquisition . This research on the use of subtitles applies quantitative methods in carrying out research. They inspect the final product, not the process. However, there are also some studies that use more qualitative methods to investigate learners' interactions with films with L1

and/or L2 subtitles and whether L1 or L2 subtitles can improve learners' language skills (Katchen, 1996b). This research focused on bottom-up language acquisition and was intended to examine learners' language acquisition through watching films with L1 or L2 subtitles. Additionally, since Ratkovic-Njegovan, Vukadinoviĭ and Nešiy-Grubiĭ (2011) noted that “according to some recent studies (UNICEF u Srbiji, 2005 – 2009), young people in Serbia are less interested in social issues outside their peer circle , tends to reject any authority, does not show awareness or enthusiasm for important social causes in general” (p. 658) This research also aims to investigate students' interest in several cultural issues and their reflections on language learning.

METHOD

This research took place at UINSU campus II, MPI 2 semester 2 study program, precisely on Jl William Iskandar, Pasar V, kec. Medan Perjuangan, Medan city, North Sumatra Province. This research took place within one day on May 29 2024. This research method uses qualitative methods, in which observations are made regarding interviews, from the results of these observations you can find out how to improve your listening comprehension. English language students where research in the MPI 2 semester 2 class, after that learning using the method of watching films and tests with students, documentation was taken during the learning process with students when learning was in progress.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Uinsu which is located on Jl. William Iskandar Ps. V, Medan Estate, District. Percut Sei Tuan, Deli Serdang Regency, North Sumatra 20371 is the target of research activities where students have all reached adulthood. Before carrying out this observation, our group consisting of 4 students had carried out guidance with Mr. Yani Lubis SAg M.Hum to conducted research on improving English listening comprehension in mpi 2 students. It was noted that students had difficulty in English listening comprehension of what they heard in English for example Worcestershire (WOOS-tur-sheer) - This word is often used in cooking and refers to a type of sauce. The pronunciation is quite challenging because of the combination of vowels and consonants, Nostalgia (naw-stahl-jee-uh) - This word refers to a sentimental longing for the past, Chatty (gah-ROO-luhs) - This word refers to someone who talks excessively. The pronunciation is quite difficult because of the combination of vowels and consonants. The pronunciation is often difficult for non-native speakers because of the combination of vowels and consonants.Limited listening abilities in English cause problems,Limited Listening Ability,Vocabular Limitations,Limited Ability to Make Inferences,Limited Ability to Make Analysis,Limited Ability to Make Conclusion

From these problems, there are several stages that are trying to be solved so that Uinsu students have increased ability to listen to English, especially English in the form of terms used every

day, namely by the method: 1) listen to English music, 2) listen to language radio English, 3) follow English-language podcasts, 4) follow English-language TV programs without subtitles. From these steps, the results show that there is an increase in their ability to listen to everyday terms in English. The first is listening to English music, in where students are given time to listen to English songs in small groups and the observation team assesses how capable the students are of mastering everyday pronunciation in English. The second stage, namely the presentation of the material, was carried out by the observation team by showing English language films.

After delivering the material, the researchers then began to appoint several students to pronounce English vocabulary and sentences in English. From the research results it can be seen, while learning, they are able to improve their listening in English, correct their friends' mistakes, produce words quite well in listening comprehension in English. When compared with the listening skills carried out by students before learning activities, students are more adept at using and mastering English conversation, especially in listening in everyday English according to the correct context.

Then, after completing the auditory comprehension lesson that had been taught, they were able to hear words from films, radio and music well. After that, the researchers tested the students by saying sentences in English. The research results obtained clearly showed that the students were able to understand and master listening comprehension in English well and correctly.

CONCLUSION

Improving English Listening Comprehension for UINSU MPI 2 semester 2 students is quite good at improving English listening comprehension, students are even able to understand the meaning of English just by listening. It doesn't stop there, students also understand the meaning of every word, sentence, even paragraph to improve students' understanding. They also do exercises to improve students' listening comprehension in English. The training that students do is watching films without subtitles, listening to music in English, listening to English radio, and watching English podcasts, then students also increase their vocabulary by memorizing them and applying them in everyday life when speaking so they don't forget easily.

REFERENCES

- Suryana, L., Hidantikarnillah, V., & Ikmi Nur Oktavianti. (2020). Enhancing Students' English Speaking Skills through Web-Based Teaching. *Eduvelop*. 3(2), 90-104. <https://doi.org/10.31605/eduvelop.v3i2.601>
- Tampubolon Sahlan, Usman, S., & Srisofian, S. (2018). The Effect of English Laboratory Use in Speaking Ability. *International Journal of Research and Reviews*, 5(9), 177-183.
- Tambunsaribu, G & Galingging, Y. (2021). Problems Faced by English Learners in Understanding English Lessons. *Dialectics: Journal of Language, Literature and Culture*, 8 (1) 30- 41.
- Baltova, I. (1999). Multisensory language teaching in a multidimensional curriculum: the use of authentic bimodal video in core French. *Canadian Modern Language Review*, 56(1), 32-48.
- Silaški, N & T.Đurović (2013). Of “siliconaires” and “millionerds” – How ESP learners understand novel blends in English. *Iberica* 25, 85-106.
- Tomalin, B. (1986). *Video, TV & Radio in the English Class*. London: Macmillan.
- Abbott, M. (2002). Using music to promote L2 learning among adult learners. *TESOL journal* , 11.
- Shen, C. (2009). Using English songs: an enjoyable and effective approach to ELT. *English language teaching* , 2, 88-94.